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DEVELOPMENT AND CHARACTERIZATION OF STAVUDINE NIOSOMES

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ABSTRACT

Niosomes are non-ionic surfactant vesicles obtained on hydration of synthetic nonionic surfactants, with or without incorporation of cholesterol or other lipids. They are vesicular systems similar to liposomes that can be used as carriers for amphiphilic and lipophilic drugs. The main aim of this study is to formulate niosomes as carriers for delivery of Stavudine. Stavudine niosomes were prepared by ether injection method and thin film hydration method using drug, non-ionic surfactants (Span 20 and Span 80) and cholesterol in the ratio of (1:2:2, 1:4:2). The prepared niosomes were evaluated for the particle size and entrapment efficiency. The four formulations were prepared by thin film hydration and four formulations were prepared by ether injection method. All eight formulations were compared for the evaluation parameters. The *in-vitro* drug release studies were performed for all the formulations (F1-F8) in phosphate buffer pH 7.4. Among the four formulations F4 formulation containing span 80 prepared by ether injection method was found to be best with entrapment efficiency of 79.42%, mean vesicular diameter of 4.80 μm and percentage of drug release was found to be 90.23%. Among the four formulations of thin film hydration technique F8 formulation containing span 80 was found to be best with entrapment efficiency of 83.25%, mean vesicular diameter of 2.41 μm . The percentage of drug release was found to be 96.12%. The encapsulation efficiency was found to increase when the surfactant concentration increases. The drug release for all the formulations was found to be zero order, which indicated that the drug release is independent of concentration and further the mechanism of drug release was found to be diffusion controlled drug release. On comparing the all formulations of these two techniques F8 was considered as best formulation because of its more entrapment efficiency, high *in-vitro* drug release rate and greater stability.

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INTRODUCTION

Niosomes are colloidal particles formed from the self-assembly of non-ionic surfactants in aqueous medium resulting in closed bilayered structures. The assembly into closed bilayers is not always spontaneous and requires input of external energy such as heat or shearing forces. Niosomes were first reported as a feature of cosmetic industry in the seventies and have been used in cosmetic formulations devised by L'Oreal and since then niosomes were extensively studied as an alternative drug delivery system to liposomes. Niosomes are microscopic lamellar structures ranging between 10 to 1000 nm which constitute of non-ionic surfactants and cholesterol. Biodegradability, biocompatibility, chemical stability, low production cost, easy storage and handling and low toxicity are the main benefits for developing niosomal systems. Niosomes can be administrated through various routes such as oral, parenteral, topical, ocular, etc. Niosomes are preferred over liposomes because the former exhibit high chemical stability and economy.

Stavudine is used along with other medications to treat human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) infection. Stavudine is belongs to the class of medications called nucleoside reverse transcriptase inhibitors (NRTIs). It works by decreasing the amount of HIV in blood. Although stavudine does not cure HIV, it may decrease the chance of developing acquired immunodeficiency syndrome (AIDS) and HIV related illnesses such as serious infections or cancer. [6] This drug has shorter half life, Negligible protein binding. The oral absorption rate of stavudine is over 80%. Stavudine is an analog of thymidine. It is phosphorylated by cellulose kinases into active triphosphate. Stavudine triphosphate inhibits the HIV reverse transcriptase by competing with natural substrate, thymidine triphosphate. It also causes termination of DNA replication by incorporating into the DNA strand. [7]

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Stavudine was purchased from yarrow chem. products, mumbai, India. Cholesterol, span-80, span-20 was procured from Loba chemicals and S.D. Fine chemicals, Mumbai, India. Methanol, Merck-specialities private limited, Mumbai. Sodium hydroxide pellets Thermo fischer scientific india pvt.Ltd. Mumbai. Diethyl ether, Merck-specialities private limited, Mumbai. Potassium di hydrogen phosphate Merck-specialities private limited, Mumbai.

Ether Injection Methods:3,4

Drug, span 20 and span 80, cholesterol were taken in prescribed ratio (1:2:2, 1:4:2) in a 250 ml beaker. The mixture was dissolved in diethyl ether and methanol (8:2) solution and slowly injected through 14 gauge needle in to a beaker containing Stavudine in 10 ml. phosphate buffer pH 7.4 the temperature maintained during the injection was 40-60 °C. The difference in temperature between phases causes rapid vaporization of ether, methanol resulting in spontaneous vesiculation.

Table no.1: Composition of Niosomal Formulations by Ether Injection method.

Formulation/Ingredients (mg)	F1	F2	F3	F4
Drug	40	40	40	40
Span 20	80	160	-	-
Span 80	-	-	80	160
Cholesterol	160	80	80	80

Thin film hydration Method: 5

Drug, span 20 and span 80 and cholesterol were taken in various ratios (1:2:2, 1:4:2) and transferred in to a clean round bottom flask. Then diethyl ether and methanol (8:2) solution was added and the flask was fixed to rotary evaporator at 50° c temp, for 20 mins under vaccum at 50 rpm. It forms a dry thin film along the sides of the R.B. flask. Stavudine dissolved in phosphate buffer pH 7.4 and was added to the thin film and vortexed at room temperature for 20 mins which forms milky white suspension.

Table no.2: Composition of Niosomal Formulations by thin film hydration method.

Formulation/Ingredients (mg)	F5	F6	F7	F8
Drug	40	40	40	40
Span 20	80	160	-	-
Span 80	-	-	80	160
Cholesterol	80	80	80	80

CHARACTERIZATION OF NIOSOMES:

Physical appearance of niosomal suspension:

The prepared niosomal suspension was viewed by naked eye to characterize color and physical state of suspension. Niosomal suspension was also viewed by optical microscope at 40 X magnification, to observe crystal characteristics of suspension by spreading a thin layer of niosomal suspension on a slide and placing the cover slip on it. The appearance for each formula was checked such as color, consistency and fluidity and comparison of each one with the other.

Vesicle size analysis:

Size and size distribution studies were done for niosomes. The suspension of niosomes was observed under optical microscope at 40x magnification. The sizes of 100 vesicles were measured using a calibrated ocular and stage micrometer fitted in the optical microscope.

Vesicle morphology:

Shape and surface morphology of niosomes was studied using scanning electron microscopy (SEM). The niosomes formed were mounted on an aluminum stub with double-sided adhesive carbon tape. The vesicles were then sputter-coated with gold/palladium using a vacuum evaporator and examined with the scanning electron microscope equipped with a digital camera at 25kV accelerating voltage.

Drug encapsulation efficiency: 6

Niosomal suspension (5ml) was placed in a glass tube. The aqueous suspension was sonicated in a sonicator bath for 15 min. The stavudine containing niosomes were separated from untrapped drug by centrifugation at 13000 rpm at 20°C for 90 min. The supernatant was taken and diluted with phosphate buffer of PH 7.4. And the free drug concentration in the resulting solution was assayed by the UV spectroscopic method at 266 nm.

$$EE\% = (\text{amount of drug entrapped} / \text{total amount added}) \times 100$$

In-vitro Drug Release Study: 7,8,9

The In-vitro release studies on niosomal suspension was performed using open ended tube which acts like donor compartment. The capacity of receptor compartment was 100 ml pH7.4 phosphate buffer placed in 250 ml beaker. The membrane was mounted between the donor and receptor compartment. A weighed amount of niosomal suspension was placed on one side of the membrane. The receptor medium taken was 100 ml of phosphate buffer of pH 7.4. The receptor fluid was stirred by a Teflon-coated magnetic bead fitted to a magnetic stirrer. The receiver fluid was stirred with a magnetic stirrer at a speed of 500 rpm. At each sampling interval, 5 ml were withdrawn and were replaced by equal volumes of fresh receptor fluid on each occasion. The Sink condition was maintained throughout the experiment. Samples withdrawn were suitably diluted and analyzed spectrophotometrically at 266nm. The percentage drug release was calculated using calibration curve of the drug in phosphate buffer of pH 7.4.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:**Vesicle morphology**

The morphology of niosomes was studied using Scanning Electron Microcopy. SEM images of stavudine revealed that the niosomes were spherical in shape and discrete with sharp boundaries having large internal aqueous space. SEM images of niosomes produced from optimized Ether Injection & Thin film hydration method formulation (F4 and F8) shows in Fig .1&2

Fig .1.

Fig .2.

Vesicle size analysis:

Results of vesicle size of stavudine niosomes are presented in (Table 3). Which indicated that vesicle formed with span 80 is smaller in size than vesicle formed with span 20. The relationship observed between niosome size and shape hydrophobicity has been attributed to the decrease in surface energy with increasing hydrophobicity resulting in smaller vesicles. Vesicles prepared by thin film hydration method were small in size compared to vesicles prepared with ether injection method, due to rotation applied during thin film hydration method.

Table No.3: Average vesicle size of F1-F8 formulation.

Formulation code	Average vesicle size in μm
F1	6.85
F2	6.01
F3	5.42
F4	4.80
F5	5.82
F6	4.71
F7	3.57
F8	2.41

Drug encapsulation efficiency:

As the surfactant content of the formulation increased, the encapsulation of drug also increased. The formulations (F1-F4) containing 1:2:2, 1:4:2 ratio of drug: surfactant: cholesterol prepared by ether injection method shows low encapsulation efficiency compared to the formulations (F5-F8) containing 1:2:2, 1:4:2 ratio of drug: surfactant: cholesterol prepared by thin film hydration method.

Table no.4 Niosomal formulations for Encapsulation efficiency.

Formulation code	% Entrapment efficiency
F1	68.34 \pm 0.45
F2	71.17 \pm 0.78
F3	75.92 \pm 0.56
F4	79.42 \pm 0.29
F5	72.33 \pm 0.87
F6	76.12 \pm 0.18
F7	80.52 \pm 0.97
F8	83.25 \pm 0.57

All values represent mean standard deviations \pm SD (n=3).

Fig-3 Drug encapsulation Efficiency.

In vitro drug release Study:

The niosomal formulations of stavudine (F1-F8) were characterized for their drug permeation study using open ended tube through an artificial membrane. Drug diffusion study of all the formulations was carried out in phosphate buffer of pH 7.4 for 24 hrs at $37 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$ with 500 rpm speed. Samples were withdrawn at regular intervals (0,1,2,3,4,5,6,8,10,12,24h) at every interval, 5ml of sample was withdrawn. After appropriate dilution the sample solution were analyzed at 266 nm for stavudine by using uv-visible spectrophotometer and cumulative % of drug released was calculated and plotted against time are shown in Figure No.4&5.

Fig 4. Cumulative percent drug release profile of Stavudine niosomal formulations (F1-F4).

Fig 5. Cumulative percent drug release profile of Stavudine niosomal formulations (F5-F8)

Release kinetics studies:

In order to understand the kinetic and mechanism of drug release, the result of in vitro drug release study of niosomes were fitted with various kinetic equation like Zero order (cumulative % release vs. time), First order (log % drug remaining vs. time), Higuchi's model (cumulative % drug release vs. square root of time), Peppas plot (log of cumulative % drug release vs. log time). R^2 and n values were calculated for the linear curve obtained by regression analysis shown in table No 5.

Table No 5. Correlation coefficient values Stavudine niosomal formulations F1-F8.

Formulation code	Correlation coefficient various release kinetics				
	Zero order	First order	Higuchi	Peppas	
	R ²	R ²	R ²	R ²	n
F1	0.994	0.960	0.930	0.802	1.024
F2	0.992	0.944	0.928	0.767	1.003
F3	0.991	0.940	0.938	0.794	1.046
F4	0.986	0.934	0.946	0.750	1.010
F5	0.996	0.931	0.918	0.802	1.044
F6	0.994	0.923	0.924	0.776	1.026
F7	0.990	0.922	0.936	0.779	1.047
F8	0.984	0.911	0.950	0.732	1.015

Stability studies

The niosomal dispersion showing highest entrapment efficiency (F8) was stored in three different temperatures $4 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$, $25 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$, and $45 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$. The encapsulation efficiency and vesicle size was again calculated after 2 months. Stability testing are shown in Table No.6.

Table No 6: Stability studies of optimized formulations (F8).

S.No.	Temp.(^o c)	Initial		After 2 months	
		Vesicle size	Encapsulation efficiency	Vesicle size	Encapsulation efficiency
1	$4 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$	3.52 ± 0.43	92.14 ± 0.56	3.50 ± 0.67	91.01 ± 0.46
2	$25 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$	3.52 ± 0.43	92.14 ± 0.56	3.48 ± 0.34	89.32 ± 0.56
3	$45 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$	3.52 ± 0.43	92.14 ± 0.56	3.42 ± 0.95	90.73 ± 0.32

CONCLUSION

The main aim of this study is to formulate niosomes as carriers for delivery of Stavudine. Stavudine niosomes were prepared by ether injection method and thin film hydration method using drug, non-ionic surfactants (Span 20 and Span 80) and cholesterol in the ratio of (1:2:2, 1:4:2). The prepared niosomes were evaluated for the particle size and entrapment efficiency. The four formulations were prepared by thin film hydration and four formulations of were prepared by ether injection method. All eight formulations were compared for the evaluation parameters. The *in-vitro* drug release studies were performed for all the formulations (F1-F8) in phosphate buffer pH 7.4. Among the four formulations F4 formulation containing span 80 prepared by ether injection method was found to be best with entrapment efficiency of 79.42%, mean vesicular diameter of $4.80 \mu\text{m}$ and percentage of drug release was found to be 90.23%. Among the four formulations of thin film hydration technique F8 formulation containing span 80 was found to be best with entrapment efficiency of 83.25%, mean vesicular diameter of $2.41 \mu\text{m}$. The percentage of drug release was found to be 96.12%. The encapsulation efficiency was found to increase when the surfactant concentration increases. It was apparent that *in vitro* release of stavudine showed slow drug release. In order to describe the release kinetics of all eight formulations the corresponding dissolution data were fitted in various kinetic dissolution models like zero order, first order, Higuchi, and Peppas respectively. As indicated by higher R² values, the drug release from all formulations follows zero order release and Higuchi model. Since it was confirmed as Higuchi model, the release mechanism was diffusion controlled.

The Peppas model is widely used to confirm whether the release mechanism is Fickian diffusion, nonFickian diffusion or zero order. 'n' value could be used to characterize different release mechanisms. The 'n' values for all formulations were found to be more than 0.89. This indicates that the release non-Fickian diffusion mechanism. On comparing the all formulations of these two techniques F8 was considered as best formulation because of its more entrapment efficiency, high *in-vitro* drug release rate and greater stability.

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